



Figure: Benchmarked GHOST and Dedalus pseudo-spectral numerical solvers. For a freely decaying shear layer, (a) the total kinetic energy of the system (mean + fluctuations) decreases rapidly. (b) The KH instability generates magnetic energy, which first grows, then saturates, and eventually decays (not shown). All the phases and time oscillations are accurately captured by both solvers. (c) The magnetic energy spectrum, which is computed when magnetic energy reaches its peak, is identically reproduced by both solvers. For a forced shear layer, (d) the total kinetic energy does not decay as in (a) and remains above the energy in the mean flow. (e) The z-integrated energy is decomposed by horizontal Fourier mode numbers (m,n) in both runs using Dedalus (represented by D) and GHOST (represented by G). It is observed that the two solvers perfectly reproduce the growth of the instability and nonlinear excitation of linearly-stable wavenumbers, for example, (m,n)=(0,1). (Other extensive benchmark calculations and longer runs were performed in the beginning of the project.)